

Titrimetric Determination of Thorium(IV) Using 1,2-Diaminocyclohexane-N,N,N',N'-tetraacetic Acid as Titrant and Pyrocatechol Violet as Indicator

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A simple and convenient method for the direct titrimetric determination of thorium(IV) at micro gram level has been developed, using 1,2-diaminocyclohexane-N,N,N',N'-tetraacetic acid (DCTA) as a titrant and pyrocatechol violet (PCV) as an indicator around pH 2.5-3.0. The colour change is from blue violet to yellow. The optimum range for the estimation was 36 μ g to 72.41 mg per 25 ml. The rsd for 24 samples in three different concentrations in the optimum range was found to be 0.79 to 0.21%. The optimum conditions like pH, concentration of DCTA, concentration of indicator, temperature and tolerance limits for foreign ions were also established. The method is useful for the determination of thorium in monazite.

DIRECT titrimetric methods for the determination of thorium(IV) using aminopolycarboxylic acids as titrants are but few. In many of the earlier methods disodium salt of EDTA was used as titrant¹⁻³. Apart from EDTA, nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA)⁴, and disodium salt of anthranilic-N,N-diacetic acid (ANDA)⁵ were also introduced for the direct titration of thorium(IV) with some indicators. 1,2-Diaminocyclohexane-N,N,N',N'-tetraacetic acid (DCTA) has been tried as a titrant using pyrocatechol violet (PCV) as an indicator. The details of the study are reported here.

Experimental

A 0.1 M stock solution of thorium nitrate [Th(NO₃)₄·6H₂O], A.R., (Fisons, Philadelphia) was prepared with a few drops of nitric acid to prevent hydrolysis of the salt and was standardized gravimetrically⁶. A 0.1 M stock solution of DCTA (Merck, Pro analysi) was prepared in distilled water with a few drops of sodium hydroxide to give a clear solution. A 0.1% aqueous solution of PCV (Loba, Bombay) was used.

All other solutions were prepared from A.R./G.R. quality chemicals in distilled water.

Procedure :

The solution of thorium(IV) is diluted until it contains 72.41 to 2.41 mg of the metal per 25 ml solution. The pH is adjusted to 2.5-3.0 by addition of acid or alkali, using pH meter and 2-3 drops of PCV solution are added. The mixture is titrated with 0.01 M DCTA solution till the colour changes from blue-violet via pink to lemon-yellow. At lower concentrations of thorium i.e. 2.41 to 0.48 mg per 25 ml and 0.48 mg to 36 μ g per 25 ml, 0.001 M and 0.0005 M DCTA solution respectively was used for the titration.

One ml 0.01 M DCTA is equivalent to 2.321 mg thorium.

Results and Discussion

pH variation : One ml 0.01 M solution of thorium was taken and diluted to 25 ml, pH adjusted to different values between 1.5 to 3.5 and titration was carried out. It was found that the end point was sharp between pH 2.5 to 3.0. Below this pH the end point was diffused and above this, erratic values were obtained. Between pH 2.5 to 3.0 the results were accurate and reproducible. In all further experiments pH 2.8 \pm 0.2 was maintained.

DCTA variation : To estimate thorium at different levels of its concentrations, suitable concentrations of DCTA were used. (0.01 M for 72.41-2.41 mg Th per 25 ml ; 0.001 M for 2.41-0.48 mg Th per 25 ml and 0.0005 M for 0.48 mg - 36 μ g Th per 25 ml).

Indicator variation : The indicator was varied from 1 to 5 drops of 0.1% aq. solution and it was found that in all the cases the end point was sharp with 2 to 5 drops ; 2 drops of indicator were therefore used in further titrations.

Temperature study : The end point was sharp even at room temperature throughout the thorium concentration range, although results are accurate upto 60°.

Range and relative standard deviation : According to the procedure described above the optimum concentration of thorium that can be titrated was found to be 0.036 mg to 72.41 mg Th per 25 ml. Below and above this range the end point was not sharp. Relative standard deviations of 24 samples in 3 different concentrations of thorium (0.036 mg/25 ml, 1.20 mg/25 ml and 2.41 mg/25 ml) in the optimum

range was found to be 0.79, 0.44 and 0.21%, respectively.

Effect of foreign ions: The following ions (mg) do not show any significant error in the estimation of 0.96 mg thorium in 25 ml according to the procedure described above: K^+ (1700.00); Sr^{2+} (750.00); Ag^+ (250.00); Mn^{2+} (200.75); Ca^{2+} (240.47); Mg^{2+} (187.96); Hg^{2+} (210.00); Ba^{2+} (880.00); Ce^{3+} (150.00); Zn^{2+} (90.00); rare-earths (28.00); U^{6+} (12.5); Cr^{3+} (10.00); Li^+ (6.00); Cd^{2+} (1.98); B^{3+} (0.62); Al^{3+} (0.01); Co^{2+} (0.13); Fe^{3+} (0.06); W^{6+} (0.06); Pb^{2+} (0.60); Cu^{2+} (0.1); Ti^{4+} (0.003); Zr^{4+} (0.0006); Ni^{2+} (0.0005); Sn^{2+} (0.000001); SO_4^{2-} (0.0068); PO_4^{3-} (0.007); CH_3COO^- (21.87); $C_2O_4^{2-}$ (0.05); F^- (0.00004); tartrate (0.0002).

However, at higher concentrations the interference is observed for Ti^{4+} , Zr^{4+} , Ni^{2+} , Sn^{2+} , SO_4^{2-} , PO_4^{3-} , F^- and tartrate by blocking the indicator response.

Thorium(IV) forms a blue-violet complex with PCV at pH 2.5-3.0 and by titration with DCTA this blue-violet colour is changed via pink to lemon-yellow around pH 2.8. This reaction has been utilized for the direct titrimetric determination of very low concentration of thorium(IV) ($36 \mu\text{g}/25 \text{ ml}$) using PCV as an indicator. Since the titration is carried out at pH 2.8 comparatively few cations form complexes with DCTA of sufficient strength to interfere. Thorium can be estimated in presence of the foreign ions mentioned above. The method finds use in the determination of thorium in monazite after the separation of thorium and lanthanides from rest of the elements⁷.

1.95 g monazite after decomposition with conc. sulphuric acid, was dissolved in ice-cold water, saturated with H_2S , filtered, H_2S boiled off and the solution made upto 250 ml. From 100 ml of this solution thorium and rare-earths were precipitated with 10% oxalic acid, filtered, precipitate ignited in

a platinum crucible, dissolved in conc. HCl and made upto 100 ml and used for titrations. For comparison purpose thorium in monazite was also estimated by EDTA-PCV⁸ method and the results are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS OF MONAZITE

Sl. No.	Volume of monazite sample soln. taken (ml)	EDTA ¹ 0.01 M (ml)	Estimated Th (mg)	DCTA ² 0.01 M (ml)	Estimated Th (mg)
1.	6.0	1.80	4.178	1.80	4.178
2.	8.0	2.40	5.570	2.40	5.570
3.	10.0	3.00	6.963	3.00	6.963

1. For EDTA titration: Dilution=25 ml; pH=3.0; PCV indicator=3 drops.
2. For DCTA titration: Dilution=25 ml; pH=2.8; POV indicator=2 drops.

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